

Annexure No.:2

PROFORMA

THE EFFECT OF CARBETOCIN VERSUS OXYTOCIN ON VITAL PARAMETERS OF PARTURIENT UNDERGOING ELECTIVE CAESAREAN SECTION- A RANDOMIZED DOUBLE BLINDED STUDY IN INDIAN RURAL POPULATION.

Registration number in study:

Name :

Age:

Education:

Occupation:

Place of residence:

Socioeconomic status:

Height:

Weight:

Body Mass Index (BMI):

Last menstrual period:

Expected date of delivery:

Obstetric score:

Indication for elective caesarian section:

(1)		(11)		(21)		(31)		(41)		(51)	
(2)		(12)		(22)		(32)		(42)		(52)	
(3)		(13)		(23)		(33)		(43)		(53)	
(4)		(14)		(24)		(34)		(44)		(54)	
(5)		(15)		(25)		(35)		(45)		(55)	
(6)		(16)		(26)		(36)		(46)		(56)	
(7)		(17)		(27)		(37)		(47)		(57)	
(8)		(18)		(28)		(38)		(48)		(58)	
(9)		(19)		(29)		(39)		(49)		(59)	
(10)		(20)		(30)		(40)		(50)		(60)	

TABLE DEPICTING THE HEART RATE AFTER (EACH) MINUTE

After a period of	5 min	10 min	15 min	20 min	25 min	30 min	35 min	40 min	45 min	50 min	55 min	60 min
Systolic Blood Pressure												
Diastolic Blood Pressure												
Which additional uterotonics were administered and in what dosage ? (if applicable)												
Tone of uterus (in a linear analogue scale from 1 to 10)												

TABLE DEPICTING OTHER OBSERVATIONS

After a period of	5 min	10 min	15 min	20 min	25 min	30 min	35 min	40 min	45 min	50 min	55 min	60 min
Nausea												
Vomiting												
Flushing												
Feeling of warmth												
Headache												
Other (if any, then please specify)												

TABLE DEPICTING INFORMATIONS REGARDING SIDE EFFECTS

Hemoglobin pre-operatively:

Hemoglobin post-operatively: